

Does ICT Cause Innovation? Evidence from Ghana

Amaama Abdul Malik*^{ID}, Sadik Jibreal^{ID}
İbn Haldun University, Dept. of Economics, İstanbul, Türkiye
Nişantaşı University, Dept. of Business Administration, İstanbul, Türkiye
*Corresponding author: amaama.abdulmalik@stu.ihu.edu.tr

Abstract

Innovation has become the priority of most nations for the last two decades. This has been seen in the increase in expenditure on the investment in Research and Development (R&D) and Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The adaptation and diffusion of innovation depends on the policies put in place by the government and firms to attract foreign investors. The ICT sector in Ghana has seen massive development and has contributed a lot to the development of the economy of the country through providing employment and making communication and other technological works easy. We set out to find whether ICT promotes innovation in Ghana by looking at the impacts of exportation and importation of ICT in Ghana. We used Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model on a data from the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and the World Development Indicators (WDI). The number of patent applications is used as the amount of innovation in the country rather than the granted patents because application depicts the actual number of innovations within a year. We found that both importation and exportation of ICT increase innovation in Ghana in the short run. However, importation of ICT decreases innovation with a higher margin than the increase caused by exportation of ICT in the long run. This is as a result of the fear of failure and lack of support for innovative projects. We suggest that the government should support and bring up policies to encourage firms to innovate.

Keywords: ARDL model, Ghana, ICT, innovation, R&D

Introduction

The world economy over the last two decades has seen massive policies with regards to research and development (R&D) aiming at promoting innovation to foster economic growth in especially Europe, the US, and some Asian countries. The use of ICT has been one of the areas of interest in these researches. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) are the technological gadgets for gathering, processing, saving, and retrieving information to enhance communication. It includes the ability of an electronic devices like computer and its peripherals, network, digital cameras among others to convert information into a digital form for consumers (1).

The adaptation and diffusion of ICT in the work place depends on factors like the policies put in place by both government and the firms to attract foreign investors, the knowledge level of the workforce and the organization of the work place.(2,3) also found managers who are aligning to the adoption of ICT and the firm's strategic focus increases their productivity and their share of the market. Also, the diffusion of ICT helps firms to be more innovative through the introduction of new goods and services and responds to changes in the market demand way better (2,4,5). However, most firms or industries in Africa do incremental innovation where they built on already made invention due to the fear of failure of an initial project. Capital is very scarce in Africa so firms try to get the best off their investments and it prevent them from venturing into risky projects(6). So how does ICT lead to innovation in Ghana?

In the case of Ghana, the ICT sector since its inception has been playing a key role in the growth of the economy amidst the economy's fiscal constraints and the devaluation of the currency. The country ranked 5 in sub- Sahara Africa with respect to the size of the market and the potential for future growth (7). The sector is now valued at around \$1 billion and is expected to increase to about \$5 billion by the year 2030 (8). The ICT sector in Ghana is overseeded by the ministry of Communication and Digitalization. They are in charge of giving licenses and regulating the performance in both ICT and the communication sectors.

The ICT telecommunication sector contributed about 3.6% to the GDP of the country in 2017(9,10). The number of employment in the BPO sector a US-based firm dealing with techs in Ghana in the year 2019 was estimated to be around 6,700 (11). The number of companies providing business outsourcing

services with number of IT-packages were more than 20 and more than 50 training and mentorship hubs for startups in 2019.

The triumph of most sectors are dependent on the policies that are put in place in a country with stable environment that promote fair competition (12). The ICT sector in Ghana is governed by the ICT for Accelerated Development Policy (ICT4AD, 2003) and National Telecom Policy (NTP). The former was developed by taking into consideration the major stakeholders including the civil society, public and private sectors, and support from the United Nations UN. The aim of this policy is to transform Ghana into a society with rich information and knowledge which are ICT led (7).

Overview of the ICT Sector in Ghana

Most technological equipment, software and services companies from the USA are currently operating in Ghana and are covering the market of neighboring countries as well. These companies include Tech Gulf, Google, Parrel Wireless and cisco, among others. Google opened its first ever Artificial intelligence lab in Africa in the year 2019 in Ghana while American Tower Corporation is the leading investor when it comes to telecommunication. Also, Tech Gulf is currently creating data centers and technology startup hubs in Ghana(13).

Figure 1.1 shows the overview of the ICT sector in Ghana. The sector comprises of the broadcasting industry, telecommunication industry and finally the support services provider industry. The Telecommunication industry is the highest component of the sector and deals with the mobile network operators and service providers. The broadcasting industries deals with television and radio by looking at the registered TV and radio stations respectively. These two industries basically look at the consumption and diffusion of ICT in the country. According to the National Communication Authority, as at the end the third quarter of 2022 the number of officially registered TV stations in Ghana were 115 with 113 out of this number already airing. Also, there is over 682 authorized radio broadcasting stations in the country. The support and other services industry look mostly at the repairs and manufacturing of ICT in the country. The industry also deals with the sale and consultation services.

Figure 1. Overview of the ICT sector in Ghana

Source: National communication Authority 2018 Report, page 14

The covid 19 pandemic increased the popularity and importance of ICT leading to an increase in global digitalization. Similarly, government of Ghana as well announced digital related and technological policies to enhance and develop the ICT and digital sector for 2022 and 2023 financial years. The following were highlighted and to be achieved in the shortest possible time,

- The digitalization of fiscal revenue and the improvement in the delivery of online education.

- Digitization of address system, land records and national ID to enhance delivery services and productivity.
- Increase in national fiber and improvement in internet connectivity. Increase in digital literacy rate.
- Support for domestic technology entrepreneurs to promote innovation and export.

The main question of this study is does ICT promotes innovation at the macro level? To answer this question the following hypothesis are analyzed.

H01: The importation of ICT increase innovation in Ghana.

H02: The exportation of ICT increases innovation in Ghana.

Ha1: The importation of ICT decreases innovation in Ghana.

Ha2: The exportation of ICT decreases innovation in Ghana.

Literature Review

A country with thriving and innovative sectors leads to the creation of jobs and economic growth. (14) studied the role of ICT in the performance of innovation in medium and small scaled enterprises in the UK. The result shows that ICT operates as an enhancer to innovation within these firms while applications that are market oriented has the potential to create innovation. (4) also compared the productivity performance of 15- EU Countries and CEE countries during the 90s. They found ICT to contribute to growth in labor productivity in both sets. Also, ICT was found to be an important ingredient to growth with lesser probability of convergence. To find how the combination of R&D and ICT impact on firms,(5) compared the impact of R&D and ICT on the productivity and innovation of firms in the USA and Europe. They found a very strong positive relationship among R&D and ICT with productivity and innovation. However, firms invest less in these two ingredients. R&D improved innovation more while ICT increased productivity more. ICT and R&D were found not to complement each other. Some studies found differences in the aggregate and the sectoral growth between Europe and USA while the results for the firm levels did not show any significant difference when it comes to the impact of ICT and R&D (3).

(7) checked the contribution of ICT and the telecommunication sector to the economic growth in Ghana from 2010 to 2015. They found the highest contribution of telecommunication was in the year 2010 which declines over the remaining reference period. Also, telecommunication is the highest contributor to the ICT sector as majority of the tech manufactured or imported are used in communication. In checking how ICT adaptation enhances innovativeness in the informal sectors in Ghana and Nigeria,(15) used a binary logistic regression analysis on survey data from the World Bank Enterprise Survey in 2014. They found an increase in the innovativeness of all the firms that use email, websites, and cellphones though the impacts are disproportionate in both countries. An increase in the expenditure of research and development and the allowance of employees to voice their ideas also increased innovation. However, the adoption and diffusion of ICT in Africa especially in the rural areas is constraint due to poor technological infrastructure, inadequate skills of the users and unsuitable policies (16).

(1) found that after the implementation of the computerization in the year 2001 in Ghana, the policy was challenged due to the inability of the teachers to use computer to teach. This is because of the non-availability of computers in schools, lack of access to internet and power or electricity problems coupled with lack of technical know-how. (17) used Ordered Logit regression model on the problems of 500 entrepreneurs in Ghana. Firms who invest less in R&D and ICT were found to encounter business barriers as compared to their counterparts.

We can conclude from the literature that ICT correlates positively with innovation and productivity. Albeit, in the case of Africa and developing countries there are a lot more challenges in achieving this. The question is, in the case of Ghana how does importation and the exportation of ICT impact on the innovativeness in the sector?

Data

The number of patent application is used as the amount of innovation in the country rather than the granted patents. This is because application of patent depicts the actual number of innovations within a year but the granted patents underscore innovation as it depends on factors like the examiners reviewing the innovation which has been noted by (18). The data for the patent application is taken from World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and includes resident, non-resident, and Ghanaians from abroad. Patent application was lagged to control the variation in the data. The data available is from 2012 to the year 2021. To increase the number of observations we used E-views to transform the data

into monthly to enable us to capture the volatility of the variables. This was done by using the low to high frequency method and selecting the linear option. The linear match places the observation with the lower frequency (yearly) into the last period of the higher frequency data (monthly) and then interpolates the remaining values linearly.

Also, the independent variables import and export of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and the import of merchandise inputs for factories and industries (as a controlled variable) are taken from the world development indicators. The ICT goods that are imported and exported includes electronic components such as computers and their peripheral equipment, consumer electronic equipment and other miscellaneous goods. These two variables are measured at a percentage of total imports and exports respectively. Table 1 below shows the descriptive statistics of all the variables. All the variables are normally distributed with exception of ICT import. Imports of merchandise has both highest mean and deviation around its means while export of ICT has the least with standard deviations of 2.719668 and 0.061477 respectively.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	Patent Application	ICT Imports	ICT Exports	Merchandise Imports
Mean	2.576442	2.803048	0.122771	75.54744
Median	2.558045	2.501148	0.129139	75.32324
Maximum	4.890349	4.550805	0.256238	81.18015
Minimum	0	2.242675	0.022469	70.60675
Std. Dev.	1.18083	0.618551	0.061477	2.719668
Skewness	-0.12971	1.549541	0.029124	-0.05088
Kurtosis	2.255573	4.030884	1.892832	2.36258
Jarque-Bera	2.511762	43.11258	4.968073	1.683994
Probability	0.284825	0	0.083406	0.430849
Sum	249.9148	271.8956	11.90881	7328.102
Sum Sq. Dev.	133.8584	36.73008	0.362823	710.0731
Observations	97	97	97	97

Methodology

We used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model by (19) in this study. The model is used on time series data, and it contains the lagged value of the dependent variable, both lag and current values of the regressor. It can also use the combination of exogenous and endogenous variables. The addition of the lag dependent variable also controls for all other factors that affects innovation but are not included in the study. The model is an upgrade from (20) which makes use of a bounds testing framework to allow for the usage of variables with mixed order of integration. It also allows for the modelling of long run relationships among variables of unknown integration orders, and it handles serial correlation through the selection of the right lag order. ARDL model also provide a long run parameter that are consistent even with weakly endogenous explanatory variables (21).

Unlike other cointegration models like the Engle and Granger cointegration(22), ARDL model is more efficient with fewer sample sizes and on variables with I (0) and I (1). However, the findings of the model become unreliable when the series are stationary at the second difference I(2) (19,20). The general model is stipulated below.

$$Y_t = \partial + \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i X_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad (1)$$

where Y_t is the dependent variable in our case innovation (patent application), $\sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i Y_{t-i}$ is the summation of previous values of the dependent variable at p lags where p is maximum lags determine by the data and the writer. $\sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i X_{t-i}$ is also the summation of the independent variables and their β coefficients $i=1,2,3,\dots,q$ is the maximum number of lags for the regressors. Lastly, μ_t is the stochastic error term.

The long run impact of each regressor can be predicted by the ARDL model by using the function below:

$$X_t = \frac{\beta_0 + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \dots + \beta_q}{1 - \theta_1 - \theta_2 - \theta_3 - \dots - \theta_p} \quad (2)$$

where β is the coefficient of the independent regressors both current and lagged and θ is the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable included in the regression?

Pre-Estimation Tests

The stationarity of a series is a not a necessary condition for using ARDL model. However, to prevent the crash of the model by using an I (2) stochastic trend series, the need to check arises. Table 2 shows the stationarity of the variables by using the Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test. The test has a null hypothesis of unit root. Each of the variables are stationary at level I (0) with different levels of significance.

Table 2. Stationarity of the variables by using the Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test

Variables	In-Level
Patent application	0.0689*
ICT import	0.0547*
ICT export	0.0020***
Merchandise imports	0.0115**

NOTE: ***, ** and * represents 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels, respectively

After confirming the stationarity, we checked the cointegration and the lag length of the variables. The bound test's result helps to determine whether to specify only short run relation (ARDL model) or the combination of short and long run model (Error Correction Model). That is, the availability of cointegration in the results mean the need to specify both long run and short run while we use ARDL when there is no cointegration. The bound test has the following null and alternative hypothesis:

$$H_0: b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$H_a: b_1 = b_2 = b_3 \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

where the b_1, b_2, b_3 represents the long run coefficient of import of ICT, export of ICT and merchandise import respectively. The result of the bound test is interpreted by comparing the F-statics and the critical values; I (1) for upper band and I (0) for lower band. Following the critical values of Narayan (2005), the null hypothesis for no cointegration is not accepted at all levels of significance in Table 3 which indicates the existence of long run relationship. This means we can check for both the long run and the short run relationship of the series. Additionally, the result of the maximum lag selection is presented in Table 4. In the table, all the test criteria show the optimal lag for this study as two. After these pre-tests the explicit model to be estimated for our study is outlined as.

$$Innovation_t = \delta + \sum_{i=1}^2 \theta_i innovation_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 \beta_i ct import_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 \beta_i i ct export_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 \beta_i merchandise import_{t-i} + \forall ECT_{t-1} \mu_t \quad (3)$$

where \forall is the speed of adjustment showing how fast the variables comes back to equilibrium after a shock and ECT_{t-1} is the Error correction term of the model showing the long run relation.

Table 3. Bound test result

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	31.39173	10%	2.37	3.2
k	3	5%	2.79	3.67
		2.5%	3.15	4.08
		1%	3.65	4.66

Table 4. Lag selection

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-92.13563	NA	0.462832	2.067433	2.176362	2.111415
1	52.78636	274.2610	0.020954	-1.027664	-0.891502	-0.972686
2	100.7371	89.71431*	0.007635*	-2.037357*	-1.873964*	-1.971384*
3	100.7460	0.016488	0.007800	-2.016044	-1.825418	-1.939074
4	100.7465	0.000865	0.007971	-1.994548	-1.776690	-1.906584

Result of ARDL

We then proceed to run the ARDL model regression. The result of equation 3 is presented in table 6.1 which shows the short run relationship and the long run relationship respectively. The series with -1 attached are the coefficient of the previous year's variables. In the short run, the previous year's innovation increases the innovation of the current year by about 10 percent. The success of previous invention motivates the industry to put in more effect to innovate more. Also, the importation and exportation of ICT increases innovation in the current year but the previous year's decreases innovation. This is also the case for the importation of merchandise in Ghana, these goods are already made goods that are imported and retailed by companies to promotes innovation in the short run by 4.9% percent lesser than the importation of ICT which promotes innovation by about 13 percent. As found in similar studies like (23) and (24), the importation of ICT and merchandise promote innovation through reduced cost spillover effects for knowledge and information. As a result, the importing firms are able to recreate and innovate which enhance both domestic consumption and exportation.

Furthermore, in the longrun importation of ICT and merchandise increases innovation about 13 % and 5% respectively with export of ICT increasing innovation about 47%. Ghana imports already made ICT into the country, and these are later incremented by the support service industry who manufacture both software and hardware IT to enable local usage and export. However, most of the industries or entities consume the imported ICT without any bother to increment them due to lack of technical know-how and lack of funds to venture into such business (11,13,15,25). In most cases, firms are reluctant to innovate due to the cost involved coupled with the policies of the firms and the country, so they prefer rather to import and sell the already made merchandise and work on how to increase sale and profit. Instead of investing in innovational project they will rather invest in projects that promote their yearly sales (26).

Table 5. Short and long run results

Short Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Innovation (-1)	1.0211***	0.0161	63.2306	0.0000
ICT import	1.2816**	0.6419	1.9966	0.0490
ICT import (-1)	-1.0878	0.6199	-1.7548	0.0828
ICT export	4.78533***	0.7541	6.2660	0.0000
ICT export (-1)	-2.7757***	0.7364	-6.4852	0.0000
Merchandise imports	0.49113***	0.0432	11.3592	0.0000
Merchandise imports (-1)	-0.3841***	0.0459	-10.539	0.0000
Long Run Results				
ICT Import	1.2816	0.6419	1.9966	0.0490
ICT Export	4.7253	0.7541	6.2660	0.0000
Merchandise Imports	0.4911	0.0432	11.3592	0.0000
ECT	0.0211	0.0016	12.8099	0.0000

NOTE: ***, **, * represents 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels, respectively

Conclusion

We set out to look at how the importation and exportation of ICT affects the innovation in Ghana. The result shows that in the short run the importation and exportation of ICT increases innovation. Also, in the long run, both importation and exportation of ICT increases innovation with the later increasing Innovation way more than the former. This is as a result of incremental innovative nature of the Ghanaian industries (6). Innovation normally depends on a lot of funding and funding for entrepreneurs are scarce in Ghana. Due to this, before a firm launches an innovative project, they make sure the probability of its success is way higher in order not to waste any fund. Firms rather prefer to import already made ICTs from abroad and do not even think about how to improve upon them. However, when an industry can innovate, it motivates them to venture into more challenging projects enabling innovation in the long run (26).

To motivate and promote innovation in Ghana, government should support and bring up policies to encourage firms to innovation. This can be done by fairs and workshops where entities present their projects they are working on or planning on venturing then support is given to those with good ideas. Also, the projects or contract should be given to local firms that have the capacity and the ability to execute them rather than foreigners and those with political affiliations.

Reference

- [1] Adam Natia J, Seidu Al-hassan. Promoting teaching and learning in Ghanaian Basic Schools through ICT. *Int J Educ Dev Using Inf Commun Technol*. 2015;11(2):113–25.
- [2] Bayo-Moriones A, Lera-López F. A firm-level analysis of determinants of ICT adoption in Spain. *Technovation*. 2007;27(6–7):352–66.
- [3] Cardona M, Kretschmer T, Strobel T. ICT and productivity: Conclusions from the empirical literature. *Inf Econ Policy [Internet]*. 2013;25(3):109–25. [\[Link\]](#)
- [4] van Ark B, Piatkowski M. Productivity, innovation and ICT in Old and New Europe. *Int Econ Econ Policy*. 2004;1(2–3):215–46.
- [5] Hall BH, Lotti F, Mairesse J. Evidence on the impact of R&D and ICT investments on innovation and productivity in Italian firms. *Econ Innov New Technol*. 2013;22(3):300–28.
- [6] Robson PJA, Haugh HM, Obeng BA. Entrepreneurship and innovation in Ghana: Enterprising Africa. *Small Bus Econ*. 2009;32(3):331–50.
- [7] National Communications Authority N. Determining the Contribution of the ICT/ Telecommunication Sector to GDP in Ghana. 2018;Final Repo.
- [8] GSS. Ghana Annual Household and Income Expenditure Survey. *Ghana Stat Serv*. 2023;7823–30.
- [9] Boachie MK, Ramu K. Effect of public health expenditure on health status in Ghana. *Int J Heal*. 2016;4(1):6.
- [10] Group WB. Ghana Digital Economy Diagnostic. *Ghana Digit Econ Diagnostic*. 2019;
- [11] Aguerre C, Mastrini G. Telecommunications Regulation and Broadband Development: Implications for the Andean region. *Assoc Progress Commun*. 2002;(2000):1–12.
- [12] Outsourcing G. Outsourcing Destination Guide ICT Sector Independent Information Guide By German In Sub-Saharan. 2021;
- [13] Higón DA. The impact of ICT on innovation activities: Evidence for UK SMEs. *Int Small Bus J*. 2012;30(6):684–99.
- [14] Karakara AAW, Osabuohien E. ICT adoption, competition and innovation of informal firms in West Africa: a comparative study of Ghana and Nigeria. *J Enterprising Communities*. 2020;14(3):397–414.
- [15] Ayim C, Kassahun A, Addison C, Tekinerdogan B. Adoption of ICT innovations in the agriculture sector in Africa: a review of the literature. *Agric Food Secur [Internet]*. 2022;11(1):1–16. [\[Link\]](#)
- [16] Robson P, Economics BO-SB, 2008 undefined. The barriers to growth in Ghana. *Springer [Internet]*. 2008 Apr [cited 2022 Dec 11];30(4):385–403. [\[Link\]](#)
- [17] Crosby M. Patents, innovation and growth. *Econ Rec*. 2000;76(234):255–62.
- [18] Pesaran MH. SY. & SRJ. Bound Testing Approaches to the analysis of long run relationships. *J Appl Econom*. 2001;16(3):289–326.
- [19] Pesaran, M. Hashem ; Shin Y; and SRP. Pooled Estimation of Long-Run Relationships in Dynamic Heterogeneous Panels. 1997;
- [20] Cho JS, Greenwood-Nimmo M, Shin Y. Recent developments of the autoregressive distributed lag modelling framework. *J Econ Surv*. 2023;37(1):7–32.
- [21] Engle RF, Granger CWJ. *Linkage_Study_of_Gamma_Globulin_Groups.pdf*. 1987.
- [22] Chen Z, Zhang J, Zheng W. Import and innovation: Evidence from Chinese firms. *Eur Econ Rev*.

2017;94:205–20.

- [23] Chakravorty U, Liu R, Tang R, Zhao L. Firm innovation under import competition from low-wage countries. *World Econ.* 2023;(6569).
- [24] Robson PJA, Obeng BA. The barriers to growth in Ghana. *Small Bus Econ.* 2008;30(4):385–403.
- [25] Bello DC, Lohtia R, Sangtani V. An institutional analysis of supply chain innovations in global marketing channels. *Ind Mark Manag.* 2004;33(1):57–64.